

Explore a Cold-Water Coral Reef

Just like their tropical cousins, cold-water coral reefs provide a habitat for many different creatures, which find shelter, food and even a safe place to lay their eggs amongst the coral. The coral reef is made up of living coral and dead coral 'rubble' - can you work out where most of the creatures like to stay? This reef is part of the Logachev Mounds on Rockall Bank, a large underwater landscape to the west of the UK around 600-1000m deep. Different scientists will look at hundreds of photos and videos to work out what lives around the reef. What can you find?!

	Tick	How many did you find?
Crab	<input type="checkbox"/>	4
Carrier Crab	<input type="checkbox"/>	6
Long-spine slate pen/pencil sea urchin	<input type="checkbox"/>	20 (4 groups of 5)
Brown Urchin	<input type="checkbox"/>	4
Black Coral with Skate eggs	<input type="checkbox"/>	4
Black Coral (<i>Leiopathes sp</i>)	<input type="checkbox"/>	4
Basket star	<input type="checkbox"/>	2
Octopus	<input type="checkbox"/>	2
Oreo	<input type="checkbox"/>	3
Ghost Shark/Rabbitfish	<input type="checkbox"/>	1
Pink Red Rockling	<input type="checkbox"/>	5
Blackbelly Rosefish	<input type="checkbox"/>	4
Shrimp	<input type="checkbox"/>	20
Zoanthids	<input type="checkbox"/>	3 (clusters/groups)
Red Scorpionfish	<input type="checkbox"/>	1

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